

Interaction of Electrolytes with Alumina in Aqueous Medium

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Alumina is the most widely employed adsorbent in chromatography. Owing to its amphoteric nature, it is able to combine with acids and bases by exchange. The adsorptive power of this substance is considerably influenced by grain size distribution, surface properties and water content. Although separations in chromatography are generally carried out with nonaqueous eluents, the activity of alumina depends on its water content. For the preparation of alumina of the first degree of activity, the substance is usually heated dull red, and allowed to cool in a desiccator¹. Aluminium hydroxide which had been dehydrated by heating to various temperatures was used for decomposition of ethanol². Catalysts with more than 13.8 per cent of water were found to be completely inactive.

It is accordingly thought that a great part of alumina's activity in adsorption may be lost in aqueous medium. The present work is, therefore, planned to test the adsorptive power of alumina toward certain acids and salts in aqueous media. A few studies have been reported in literature regarding adsorption by alumina from aqueous solutions. Alumina adsorbs cupric chloride from aqueous solution, but the equilibrium is not attained even after 120 hrs. of the initial uptake³. Adsorption did not cause a pH change of the medium. Sinha and Chaudhury⁴ have treated various hydrated aluminas with dilute solutions of hydrogen and sodium salts of common anions. Adsorption of the anions on the adsorbents was found to be weak, and they are completely replaced by OH⁻ of water. The dependence of electrolytic adsorption on the adsorbent to solution ratios was examined by Unland and Engel⁵ using alumina as adsorbent and certain salts including KCl, NiCl₂ and CuCl₂ as electrolytes.

All the chemicals used in this work were of Analar quality. The alumina was type 'H' as stated by the manufacturers (Peter Spence Ltd., Widnes). In carrying out an adsorption investigation, five grams of alumina were usually brought into contact with a series of solutions of varying initial concentrations of the electrolyte to be adsorbed. Each sample was suspended in a thermostat at 25° and shaken at short intervals over a period of 24 hrs. The solutions were then left to settle for few hours, after which the clear liquids above the adsorbent were analyzed to determine the amount of adsorption by difference. The usual quantitative methods were used in analysis. Adsorption from a mixture of two electrolytes on alumina was studied similarly.

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3. Fricke and Neugebauer, *Naturwiss.*, 1950, **37**, 427.
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RESULTS

Adsorption of acids: The results obtained with acetic, benzoic, hydrochloric and oxalic acids fit into the usual Freundlich equation: $N=KC^a$. The experimental data are represented as logarithmic plots in Fig. 1A. The constants, a and k are given below together with the moles of each acid adsorbed at the equilibrium concentration, C , noted in Table I.

TABLE I

acid	a	$k \times 10^6$	$C \times 10^3$	$N \times 10^6$
Acetic	0.22	64	4.72	54
Benzoic	0.33	80	4.70	60
Hydrochloric	0.12	69	4.68	64
Oxalic	0.20	51	2.25	50

It is thus shown that the alumina adsorbs from aqueous solutions no more than 6.5×10^{-3} moles per gram adsorbent even when the equilibrium concentration is 4.68×10^{-3} moles. Using nitrogen isotherm at -195° and standard BET method, the specific surface of a partially hydrated alumina, type A, has been reported recently⁷ to be $225 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, or equivalent to a monolayer of adsorbed water molecules per gram alumina, which corresponds to 3.6 m. moles⁷. The extent of adsorption could on this basis be expressed as $Q = \frac{\text{m moles acid adsorbed}}{3.6}$. The value of Q from the above data was found to be 0.015. Assuming

an adsorbed acid molecule to occupy an area which is equivalent to two water molecules, the total adsorption corresponds to a coverage of 3 percent of alumina's surface.

FIG. 1

Adsorption of the acids on alumina was found to be almost independent of temperature in the range 15–60°. Stirring of the solution has got little influence on the rate or the amount of adsorption.

Adsorption of salts: Analysis shows that the salts are molecularly adsorbed by alumina. Nearly 90% of adsorption is instantaneous, the remaining 10% takes place very slowly over a period of 10 hours or more. Fig. 2A shows graphically the results of adsorption showing obedience to Freundlich's equation. The constants, k and a are given in table II. Here also the reaction appeared to be independent of temperature in the range of 15–60°. The pH of alumina suspension is usually lowered on the addition of salts. In one case, namely, that of $CuSO_4$, the pH was initially lowered from 9.6 to 5.2 but after equilibrium was raised to 6.3.

At an equilibrium concentration of 8×10^{-3} moles in solution, the total adsorption of the electrolytes per gram alumina corresponded to 2×10^{-5} moles nickel sulphate, 7×10^{-5} moles copper sulphate and 22×10^{-5} moles silver nitrate. The chlorides of Ni and Cu behave identically with the corresponding sulphates. A part of an adsorbed electrolyte, amounting to 25 percent, could be removed by repeated washing, the cations being more strongly adsorbed than the anions.

TABLE II

Electrolyte	$k \times 10^6$	a
Silver nitrate	40	0.45
Nickel sulphate	23	0.38
Copper sulphate	80	0.11

FIG. 2

On similar assumptions to those made in the case of acids the surface coverages are 2.4, 4 and 15% respectively for nickel, copper and silver salts.

Adsorption from salt mixtures: The influence of other salts on the adsorption of copper sulphate on alumina at 25° was examined in a series of solutions in which the initial concentration of the cupric salt varied from 0.1 to 0.005 molar. Nickel sulphate was then added in sufficient amount to each solution so that the final concentration with respect to this salt was 0.2 *N*. In another identical series of solutions nickel sulphate was replaced by silver nitrate. The results are shown in fig. 2B. An instant adsorption of copper sulphate on alumina was observed but the amount adsorbed was appreciably greater in presence of the other electrolyte than when used alone. Thus, a concentration of 8×10^{-3} moles of copper sulphate alone in solution, 7×10^{-5} moles/g. were adsorbed, which in presence of silver nitrate and nickel sulphate increased to 13.5×10^{-5} and 30×10^{-5} moles respectively. In addition 44.2×10^{-5} moles of nickel sulphate were adsorbed at an equilibrium concentration of 7.7×10^{-3} moles of the salt, and similarly 42.6×10^{-3} moles of silver nitrate was adsorbed at an equilibrium of 1.8×10^{-2} moles. Taking into account the amounts of both the electrolytes adsorbed the total surface coverage increases to 40 percent in case of nickel and copper salt mixtures, and 30 percent in case of silver and copper salts mixtures.

De Boer *et al.*⁷ have observed that 24.8 mg. H₂O/100 m² still remains on aluminas dried at 120°. For a specific surface of 225 mg., about 55 mg. H₂O would thus still remain absorbed at 120°, and this amount corresponds to a surface coverage⁶ of about 85 percent. In aqueous solutions alumina is expected to be almost completely covered by at least a layer of strongly bound water molecules. The polar acid molecules or the ionized species might be expected to be adsorbed on top of this layer. The adsorption may, therefore, involve displacement of weakly bound water molecules which are attached to the top of the first layer. The magnitude of the heats of adsorption, should enable a prediction to be made as to whether the adsorbed species are directly attached to alumina, or to the already adsorbed water layer or whether they simply replace weakly adsorbed water.

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